

Experimental Article

Examples, Exceptions, and Monster Barring: Unsettling Centrism in Mathematics Education

David M. Bowers¹
University of Tennessee–Knoxville

ABSTRACT: Socratic dialogue (also referred to as Platonic dialogue) is a discursive/pedagogical technique that is used to explore questions with no clear answer, typically with a focus on surfacing inconsistencies in the learner’s thinking. I share those purposes and goals, and therefore am making use of many aspects of Socratic dialogue in this article. However, in two respects I will diverge from the common image thereof. First, Socratic dialogues typically frame exactly one speaker as the pedagogue or authority figure. However, for my goals, this is problematically reductive. It is my experience that all speakers bring unique perspective and information to the conversation, and I aim to reflect that in what I have written here—all are teachers, all are learners. Second, Socratic dialogues commonly limit themselves to the purely logical components of an argument (to the extent that we might ever consider our emotional reality separable from the wholistic reality we occupy). However, for my goals, this is again problematically reductive. The problems and questions I explore here are deeply human ones, and dehumanizing the characters comprising my play would necessarily act against that goal. Thus, within the confines of my abilities, I aim to make the characters having the discussion feel like real people—I want readers to sense hidden depths within them that even I, the author, do not have access to. Beyond perceiving humanization to be an important ethical goal in-of-itself, incorporating subjective space to which we have no access is important so as to help us keep keenly in mind that reality is and will forever be more complex than any theoretical model or research methodology can ever hope to account for. No amount of inquiry will free us of uncertainty, and that is perhaps as beautiful as it is terrifying.

KEYWORDS: *rhetorical experiment; anarchist methodology; sociopolitics of mathematics education*

¹ David M. Bowers (they/he) is a neuroqueer mathematics education researcher and radical anarchist activist whose work collectively seeks to put these different ways of knowing and moving in the world into conversation with each other, with careful attention to the ways “form” and other tacit characteristics can influence the knowledge(s) represented and conveyed in research works just as much as “content.” They currently serve as a Clinical Assistant Professor of Theory and Practice in Teacher Education at the University of Tennessee–Knoxville and can be reached via email at dbower14@utk.edu. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9467-9602>

(They walk on, as quick as one can while performing that casual strut, saunter, or swagger many of us sometimes employ when leaving difficult encounters – that nonverbal communication that we aren't hurt in any meaningful way, that our antagonists' hold no power over us. Like so many performances, it is at once a truth and a lie. T(eacher educator) holds his body tight, muscles clenched and drawn inward, eyes cast towards some sight or memory that is for his eyes only. C(ritical historian) is practically vibrating, both from keen anxiety after the experience and from thoughtfulness, cast as she was into her usual spiral of glorious wonderings and musings. M(athematicians)'s passions are turned more outward than inward – his shoulders pulled broad like he's trying to make himself look larger than he is, he gesticulates wildly as he articulates his rage following their shared experience.)

M: What the fuck was that nonsense! I need a moment to cool down. Y'all wanna duck in this dive bar and have a quiet drink before we trek on?

T: *(Muscles relax slightly, he takes a deep breath and lifts his eyes.)* You know what? Yeah. I could use that. A moment of respite in a sheltered harbor.

C: *(Nods.)* A moment of peace is always nice, but particularly welcome at the moment. *(They enter. As their eyes adjust to the dim light, they see only a few others, sitting at tables or the bar. The B(artender) dashes quietly around the room as one customer or another calls for their attention, a silent whirlwind. Wordlessly, C and T seat themselves in a quiet corner while M goes to the bar to grab their drinks.)*

C: *(After wedging herself as far into the corner of the room as she can, C lifts her eyes.)* I know, 'hashtag not all cops' or whatever, but that was just so typical and I'm just so tired.

T: *(Nodding.)* Lots of us have been tired a long time. Hegemony sits atop many colored, female, queer, poor, and disabled necks, an omnipresent violence.

M: *(Returning with drinks.)* With the weight growing exponentially along intersections. I know some of our pals are fond of the phrase “all cops are bastards,” and that one sure as hell was, but I sure as hell hope they were the exception to the rule in this city.

T: *(Sbrugs.)* I don't know... At this point in my life, I don't have a lot of trust leftover for the idea of “exceptions,” let alone when I'm talking about police.

C: *(Nodding.)* It's definitely systemic.

M: Yeah, I guess it might be the good cops that are the exception, at least round here.

T: *(Head shaking.)* It's definitely systemic, but that's not really what I mean. Examples and exceptions seem like they should be straightforward, but the way people actually use them is... troublesome. Not epistemically or anything... well, maybe that too, but what I mean is a little different. Here, let me give you an example. Y'all know I work in teacher education, so let me tell you about a problem I keep running into...

Most of the preservice teachers I work with are aiming to teach young kids. I adore these preservice teachers – they practically vibrate with energy and excitement, as if resonating

with the same energy as the children they teach. (B, temporarily free of the demands of patrons, moves energetically about the room with a rag, doing some spot cleaning.) These soon-to-be teachers come into my class with all kinds of preconceptions, some helpful and many not. For me, one of the most common and frustrating preconceptions they bring to my class is a view that young kids aren't smart or inquisitive. Like, in all my time working with young kids, they always find new and surprising ways to show me how clever and curious they are, but most of these preservice teachers don't know that 'cause they've bought into a cultural narrative that at every turn discounts knowledge in youth. It's a big deal, 'cause this is the kind of belief that can really shape how they engage with children... I see it shape both what kids can learn from a teacher and what that same teacher can learn from or about their students. It casts a translucent veil between them and their students, such that neither can really see the other. (B approaches an expensive looking piece of furniture, and whips off cloth covering it, revealing a dusty mirror which they begin cleaning.) One way teacher educators, including me, try to respond to this is with examples or cases that show off how smart children are. One go-to example I've seen is an article called "Multiplication as original sin" (Corwin, 1989). In this article, a researcher reflects on an experience they had as an elementary student where they derived their own completely valid method of multiplication, only to be chastised and publicly embarrassed by the teacher's response.

One thing I love about this article is how many of my preservice teachers can see themselves as that student. I get impassioned responses from my preservice teachers, and they seem really invested in how important it is to take the cleverness of kids seriously. It is as though the veil lifts, and for a time they see these children with clarity as young people rather than simply seeing them as "kids", genuine humans rather than these otherized things that may one day become people but aren't quite people yet. It all seems good... but then I notice something, something also observed in later research that made use of that case (Harkness & Thomas, 2008). The preservice teachers describe the kid using superlatives: Gifted, extraordinary, amazing... We had this great conversation where I thought my preservice teachers were considering an example of how smart kids are, but instead they were considering the case of that one clever kid in a room full of normies. The veil falls again, and they are looking at a room with one young person surrounded by kids. My preservice teachers and I were looking at the same thing, but I was talking about an example while they were talking about an exception. (Finishing their work, B throws the cloth back upon the mirror.)

C: (*Head cocked sideways, listening.*) Ahhhh. I think I hear what you're saying. There's this slippery slidiness to examples and exceptions. There's some kind of dominant narrative, and the case you were trying to share as a counterexample got brushed aside as an exception.

M: (*Eyes bright.*) Well, not to put too fine a point on it, but that's frustrating as hell. I know one of the reasons I initially picked mathematics is just 'cause I got tired of bickering semantics with teachers who were closed off to other reads of situations. Remember when Ms. Weekly gave me that D on that paper where I defended Hester Prynne in the Scarlet Letter? At least in math class when the teacher made a false claim I could give a counterexample and feel confident that it'd be treated seriously.

T: (*Nods.*)

C: (*Sipping drink, eyes cast into the distance.*) It shows up in historic narratives too. Like, consider antiracist activism in this country. One recurring strategy people have attempted is something Kendi (2016) called uplift suasion, a strategy he typified with the case of W. E. B. Du Bois. Y'all know the story?

T: (*Nods.*)

M: (*Cringes.*) Embarrassingly, no... If T doesn't mind, I'd love to hear more.

T: I don't mind, but you might want to refill your drink first. There's a lot to the story. (*M flags down B, indicating refills for the table, then turns his attention back to C.*)

C: (*Nods.*) Kendi tells a longer and much more detailed version of the story, but in broad strokes it goes something like this.

(*C stares intently at her drink, observing the ice wedged firmly into the bottom of the glass of amber liquid.*)

Du Bois believed, like many abolitionists before him and many reformers to this day, that racism could be persuaded away through the presentation of facts. He imagined this pursued through many avenues: Scientists could discover facts. Educators could teach the facts. Lawyers could present the facts in court. Fictional portrayals of black folk could present them in all their depth, humanity, and kindness. At marches and rallies, black folk could articulate the facts of their suffering. For his part, W. E. B. Du Bois pursued many of these, but notably tried to contribute to the abolitionist movement through his mere existence... He was, in a word, exemplary, and through the sheer force of his existence he sought to demonstrate that black folk were no lesser than white folk.

(*As the wedged ice melts, a few small pieces float to the top, their peaks poking through the liquid's surface.*)

Du Bois graduated from Harvard, he studied abroad in Europe, he taught at the college level... he was a prolific author, speaker, sociologist, and historian... He excelled at the highest levels of the white system he found himself born into. Du Bois sought to be a counterexample to the wholly negative white narrative of blackness, an example of how amazing black people could be within the standards of a system that he did not always question, perhaps most notably when race intersected with class or gender.

(*The floating ice melts, disappearing, leaving what remains wedged firmly in the bottom of the glass.*)

In the end, though, he was always written off as an exception, as an exceptional black person... or more specifically as an exceptional black, white-collar male. By the time he was in his late 50's, he wrote that "for the last two decades, [black folk] have striven by book and periodical, by speech and appeal, by various dramatic methods of agitation, to put the essential facts before the American people. Today, there can be no doubt that Americans know the facts, and yet they remain for the most part indifferent and unmoved." Uplift and persuasion had failed... He and his white audience were looking at the same examples, but his white audience was seeing exceptions, even in the case of Du Bois in of himself.

M: (*Eyes bright.*) Intense.

B: (*Finishing pouring drinks.*) Yeah, Kendi came down hard on uplift suasion as a strategy, and I really felt for that. I'm a political organizer and agitator here locally, and we have to go out of our way to educate people about this... Not all people, mind, but the more privileged their positioning the more likely we'll need to have lots of discussions about this before we can get them more active in our political organizing. Just proving that you can succeed in the system doesn't help when what we're trying to communicate is that the system is violent. Y'all need anything else right now?

M: I mean, that sounds cool as hell, and I kind of want to pick your brain more... Folk over there look like they're waving you down, but if you wanna come back and chat afterwards, I'd love to hear more about how this kind of thing plays out in what you do. This whole conversation has got me thinking.

C: (*Eyes focused, head cocked.*) Yes, I'd love to hear more too.

T: (*Smiles.*) Yeah, please swing back by. In the meantime, I gotta grill M here about how he apparently dodged this problem... for his job, at any rate.

B: (*Nods assent, leaves.*)

M: (*Laughs.*) You know, I meant what I said earlier about why I picked math, but the more I listen to y'all and the more I think about what math is like as a job instead of what it was like as a student, the more I think I didn't dodge anything.

T: (*Laughs.*) I have no idea what you mean... Are mathematicians so stuck up they won't accept your counterexamples? Not to suggest that Mathematicians are inherently stuck-up, but I've certainly known many who conveyed through words and behavior their belief that "Our truths are deeper than yours; our knowledge more pure."

C: (*Laughs.*) I wouldn't put that past them, but maybe that's my bad experiences in undergraduate mathematics talking.

M: (*Smiles.*) I know it sounds ridiculous, but when you get out of the area of sanctioned and agreed-upon knowledge in math, things change. As a student, and even as an undergraduate math major, all the math problems we did were already in the domain of "sanctioned" knowledge... A lot of re-proving stuff we already "know," so to speak. But now what I do is different than what I did then... I'm trying to learn brand new stuff, and the way mathematicians talk around and about new stuff is just... different. Not in a bad way, understand, but definitely in a way that isn't reflected in the usual math student experience. Let me tell a story to try to show what I mean. One of you got a pen? I think I need to draw a picture.

T: (*Smiles.*) You've never been able to tell a story without drawing a picture, and there's something reassuring about seeing that math definitely hasn't changed that about you.

C: (*Laughs, handing M a pen.*)

M: (*Laughs, takes pen and a napkin.*) Trying to describe my work in abstract topologic spaces is probably more than y'all want to hear, but I think I got a better story. This is a story told by Lakatos (1976) in greater detail, but I'll try to keep it short. Let's talk about polyhedrons... please contain your excitement.

(*Laughter, with C's quiet chuckles largely drowned out by T's belly laugh and M's unrestrained mirth.*)

So, y'all know what polygons are... We've got triangles, quadrilaterals, pentagons, and so forth... and each polygon has edges and vertices: Triangles got three of each, quadrilaterals have four of each, and so on.

What we're looking at, though, are polyhedrons. These are basically three-dimensional polygons. A square is a polygon, and a cube is a polyhedron... a triangle is a polygon, and a pyramid is a polyhedron. Each polyhedron has vertices and edges just like a polygon, but they also have faces. This triangular pyramid has 4 vertices, 6 edges, and 4 faces... this cube has 8 vertices, 12 edges, and 6 faces.

It was pretty obvious right away that in polygons, the number of sides is always equal to the number of corners... that is to say, the number of edges always equals the number of vertices. However, even up through the early 1700s, it was not obvious to European mathematicians what the equivalent relationship might be in polyhedra, or even if such an analogue existed. Enter Euler with a claim: $V - E + F = 2$. Vertices, minus edges, plus faces, equals two. If you have the insane urge, you can check it with the triangular pyramid and cube. The "proof" is super cool and I want desperately to share it... I am a mathematician, after all... but it's really not the point. Euler shared his ideas, and mathematicians bickered, as we are wont to do. Enter the Kepler-Poinsot star polyhedron.

A triangular pyramid consists of 4 triangular faces. A cube consists of 6 square faces. This star polyhedron consists of 12 star-pentagonal faces. Intriguingly, it also has 12 vertices and 30 edges, which means that for this polyhedron $V - E + F = -6$.

Other mathematicians responded in a variety of ways, but I want to surface one response in particular, something Lakatos called “monster barring.” Basically, for some mathematicians, this did not count as a counterexample... it was an exception. Since it was an exception, they made rhetorical moves to bar its entrance as a problematic example. Y’all can probably already guess the easiest way to do that... The star pentagon intersects itself, so you can just demand that a 3-D shape made of polygons only counts as a polyhedron if its polygonal faces don’t self-intersect.

- C:** (*Head cocked sideways, eyes closed.*) Interesting. I feel like I shouldn’t be surprised, but I kind of am.
- T:** (*Nodding.*) We’re all people, and all our practice is the practice of people. That nebulous, interstitial space between people and each other, or between people and the world... it’s always there. Like C said, there’s a slip slidiness to examples and exceptions... an interstitial space of fluid meaning navigated by well-intentioned people who remain nonetheless human.
- C:** (*Lifts eyes.*) And as we sail that sea, the inertia of the tacit and explicit societal lessons we’ve learned cast a wind that draw us back toward hegemony.
- M:** (*Smiles, rolls eyes.*) Y’all’ve always made me look bad with your casual poetry. I’m definitely hearing that “winds of society” thing, though – it fits with the pattern I’m hearing in these stories. In T’s story, the prevailing narrative is that children and receivers of knowledge, not it’s generators, and so the wind drew some of your preservice teachers to perceive that cleverness as exception. In C’s retelling of Kendi’s story of W. E. B. Du Bois, the prevailing narrative was one of black deficit, and so the wind drew white members of society to perceive his success as an exception.
- T:** Not just white members. Those winds are carried to us all, and when they assail our being they become an omnipresent violence.
- M:** Damn, yeah. Even in my math story... Euler, the guy who proposed the original polyhedral formula, is a big deal. Like, a *BIG* deal. His word carried weight, and so even if his conception of polyhedral hadn’t been a dominant narrative before, in his wake it most certainly became one... and then counterexamples became exceptions.
- C:** (*Nods.*) To try to phrase it in math-like terms, we have a thesis statement along these lines: If a marginalized group or marginalized narrative does or expresses something positive, it is rendered as an exception.
- T:** (*Nods.*) Yup, that seems about right.
- M:** (*Eyes widen.*) Oh man, that’s fucked up... I can’t believe I didn’t see it right away. Whenever I start introducing folk to formalized logic, one of the first hurdles I often see them encounter shows up when we talk about the “contrapositive” of a statement. For a statement “If P, then Q,” the contrapositive is “If *not* Q, then *not* P.” In raw logical terms, these are identical

statements, but for lots of folk that's really hard to see. "If I am dirty, then I need a shower," in raw logical terms, has the same meaning as "If I don't need a shower, then I am not dirty."

C: (*Head cocked.*) Interesting... how's that translate here?

M: The contrapositive of our thesis is "If a marginalized group or narrative does or expresses something negative, then it isn't an exception."

T: (*Laughs with exasperation.*) So, in more casual terms, the thesis is "If marginalized, then bad." Damn, that's a painfully on-point expression of societal narratives.

C: (*Shakes head.*) Frustrating. Not surprising, I guess, but baffling nonetheless. But then what about police? Police represent a dominant group and a dominant narrative, so while talking about examples and exceptions or good and bad police is still probably gonna be slippy slidy, it will undoubtedly slip in different ways.

T: (*Raises eyes to bartender.*) You catch enough of that? What do you think?

B: (*Smiling gently.*) Yeah, I think so, and I do have an answer, though I think it won't surprise you. There are a million contemporary and historical stories I could tell to set this up: Police officers caught in acts of cruelty, Hollywood producers and directors accused of sexual abuse, adults taking advantage of children, doctors dismissing the concerns of patients... In each of these stories, some version of the "bad apples" framing emerges, the same framing that, if the snippets of conversation I've overheard don't mislead me, brought you into this bar today. Oh, how our society longs to critique individuals with no attention to the systems that shaped them, gave them direction, and literally or metaphorically armed them. Those tales are powerful, but they also inundate our news feeds... you don't need me to point them out. Instead, I'm going to tell you a less intense story, but one which had a lasting impact on me by virtue of its apparent lack of intensity – it was not a shocking situation, just life-as-usual. Here's a short-version of my first experiences as an active union member, an experience I later discovered echoed the history of where I grew up (Sakai, 1983/2014).

(Other groups in the bar converse quietly, a mild susurrus against B's sonorous voice – the latter adopting a tone and cadency like one might hear from an unruly social justice activist with a megaphone.)

In my hometown, in rural Appalachia, the company I worked for after high school was fairly big and when I joined it didn't have a union. Many employees were unconcerned... It hadn't escaped their attention that their bosses were taking home more money than they were, or otherwise benefitting from the system in ways that they didn't, but their bosses mostly left them to their own devices, aside from the occasional and expected display of authority, and their wages were at least above the poverty line – something not everyone in my hometown could say. I would say my coworkers wanted more, sure, but the status quo was not so uncomfortable to drive them to fight for it.

(The susurrus of the other groups grows noticeably, but not enough to obscure B's words.)

This comfort, such as it was, did not apply to equally to everyone. People of color, queer people, women and trans people, neurodivergent and disabled people, those who had any history in sex work, those with any history of drug addiction... even people who simply didn't attend Christian worship were subject to extra scrutiny, to abuse from those in power, and to exclusion by peer groups whensoever the eye of power was cast too intently upon them. The more intersectionally marginalized we were, the more intolerable the status quo was.

(The noise of other groups conversing continues to grow. T, C, and M lean closer to B.)

Unionization was often spoken of, though always in quiet, furtive ways. Eventually, amongst those who found the status quo intolerable, some of us were able to build enough momentum to begin trying to unionize. We met in secret, hiding in the bushes metaphorically and sometimes literally. The most privileged of our coworkers stayed well-clear, afraid as they were of losing out on the good thing they felt they had going. However, over the course of a few months, we picked up lots of support and membership from our marginalized colleagues. We had big plans: We drafted contractual language to protect our marginalized peers, we examined budgets from our company and similar companies as well as productivity research to craft compelling arguments for more pay and personal time. We drafted a complete overhaul to what our workplace could look like. We formalized our union and began organizing around our demands. We began pointing to the systemic violence of our workplace, proposing our carefully crafted alternatives, and we had grown enough in support that the company had to respond – sometimes they were even driven to acquiesce to our calls for a better work environment.

(The noise of other groups is now a droning roar.)

Noticing our growing successes, our privileged peers began showing great interest in our union. Over the course of a few months, they began joining *en masse*. Inevitably, we reached a point where the relatively privileged outnumbered the intersectionally marginalized, and soon most of our elected positions were filled with the former while those of us who had begun the union were driven back to the margins. We quickly saw our carefully researched proposals gutted. The systemic problems we surfaced? New union leadership saw those as exceptions to the norm, as they certainly had no experiences of the kind. Coworkers experiencing abuse? Exceptions to the norm. Abusive floor managers? Bad apples. “Sometimes bad things happen... you can't always point the blame at the company.” We wanted change, real change, but our privileged coworkers felt that was too much to ask, for if we ask for too much, then why would the company give us anything? *(B's voice, just as strong as when they started, is now barely audible over the roar of everyone else's conversations.)* All we saw from that point until I left the company was a string of purely symbolic olive branches, extended not for my benefit, not to appease me, but to appease my privileged coworkers. Sure, they'd fight for us when the violence we were experiencing was obvious to them, but if they could find some sort of angle where it looked like our concerns were being considered, then that was “good enough,” and “all that could be expected.”

(Sudden silence.)

- T:** (*Nodding.*) Yeah, that sounds about right. Makes me think of how Leftists actually *were* and *are* calling for police abolition, but when the movement recently got inundated with those privileged enough to have avoided the fear of extrajudicial killing the language quickly softened to *defund*.
- B:** (*Nodding.*) Often with the added language of “No one is suggesting total abolition...” as if I’m not standing right here, literally asking for that.
- T:** (*Laughs.*) Exactly.
- C:** (*Eyes staring into the middle distance.*) Well, I guess we have our second thesis. If a privileged group or privileged narrative does or expresses something negative, it is rendered as an exception.
- M:** (*Grimaces, laughs awkwardly.*) Contrapositive: “If a privileged group or narrative does or expresses something positive, then it isn’t an exception.” Basically, if privileged, then good. Fucking figures.
- T:** (*Nodding.*) I guess this highlights what I meant when I said I don’t trust examples and exceptions... We all internalize our society in greater or lesser part, and part of that internalization is “privileged good, marginalized bad,” so speaking and thinking in terms of examples and exceptions might incline us to support a violent society rather than tear down a system of violence.
- M:** (*Turns towards bartender.*) This has got me thinking back to what started my friends and I down that conversation, the language of “All cops are bastards.” When I hear or see people talk about this in conversation or in social media or whatever, they end up talking about examples and exceptions, but that seems like an unhelpful track. What’s your take on the language of ACAB?
- B:** (*Smiling.*) Honestly, I get how it makes some people deeply uncomfortable, but that’s kind of the point... It can be important to sit with your discomfort, especially if you’re privileged enough that you can choose to avoid or ignore it. That discomfort is telling you something, something you need to hear.

The language of ACAB, in my view, does at least two things. First, it’s a systems-level critique that doesn’t use systems-level language... That’s a big deal for a political organizer who critiques systems, because systems-level language can be cumbersome and unapproachable even to someone with experience using that kind of language – political organizing demands accessible language. Second, it acknowledges *complicity* with the system. Again, I grew up in a small town in Appalachia, so I *knew and had gone to school with* many of our local police officers. Some of them were good friends of mine, people I would describe as good people. However, Policing is a system of violence, and ACAB expresses that complicity. I use it in other contexts too... My coworkers regularly hear me say “All managers are bastards” in spite of the fact that my job here is basically management. Using that language recognizes my own complicity, gives me a discomfort that I think it is important to sit with.

T: (*Nodding.*) I hear that.

C: (*Eyes raised, head cocked, staring intently.*) If I might ask a silly question, why is that discomfort so important to you?

B: From my time in that union... We move within and against systems in a different way when we think we can be good *within* the system than we do when we acknowledge that we can never truly be good until we tear the system down. Plus, as soon as we ended up surrounded by the comfortable, those of us who were uncomfortable felt so... gaslit? Like, if so many were apparently so comfortable, then how could our pain be real? I wonder, if my coworkers sat with their discomfort, how things might have been different.

C: (*Nodding.*) Interesting. Reflecting on my authority, and the role research and academia have played in colonization and systemic violence, I wonder if All Researchers Are Bastards too?

M: (*Laughing.*) Damn straight we are!

T: (*Chuckles.*) The districts and universities I've worked for weren't ever angelic, either. I had a lot of bad experiences with teachers as a kid, and I think that kinda drove me to where I am today, but frankly *Teachers* with a capital T still make me uncomfortable. I wonder if the same should be said of our role as teachers?

(*Everyone sits back, contemplative, leaving the question hanging in the air as the lights fade out and the play draws to a close.*)

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

Like all forms of life, works of writing such as this grow and change and evolve over time, often in ways that are difficult or impossible to anticipate in advance of the process. This particular piece started its life as a component of my dissertation (Bowers, 2021). The overall dissertation was conceived of as an exploration of my relationship with Mathematics Education research (and education research more broadly). Like so many marginalized and minoritized graduate students (e.g. queer, neurodivergent), normative mathematics education research operated in ways that regularly fell into conflict with my very being, and with the blessing of my committee (Corey Drake, Alyssa Dunn, Tonya Bartell, and Kristen Bieda) I was encouraged to push myself to explore that conflict with depth of meaning. The first core dissertation chapter I drafted, which ended up being the precursor to this manuscript, was meant to both push my thinking in terms of the substantive content it explored (examples and exceptions across difference cultural spaces), but also in terms of its form. To express the kinds of knowledge I was trying to express, which tended to be dialectical and deeply resistant to structural description, I had to break free of the much more limited rhetorical norms mathematics education researchers often confine themselves to, and this is what gave rise to the format of a play. My committee, as well as other Mathematics Education faculty and graduate students who read or heard me present, gave varied feedback, but the most important type of feedback I sought was simply this: What thoughts, discussions, or discomfort did they experience and voice as a byproduct of reading this? In other words, what visible effect was it having on their thinking and being?

All that in/direct feedback informed what this paper has become, in powerful conjunction with my peer reviewer, Meredith Dayna Levy. Meredith is a playwright whose work gives great weight to lived experience and emotional truth, especially in contexts including womanhood and queerness, and these sorts of expertise fit beautifully with what I was trying to create. Rather than focusing primarily on the content of the play the way Mathematics Education faculty and graduate students had, Meredith instead focused primarily on how we could get as much as possible out of the form of the writing. Notably, she drew my attention to qualities of the work such as characterization or the broader use of metaphor to support the tacit and explicit ideas found in the text. Here are some of the more substantial changes that Meredith supported me in creating:

Meredith identified some published plays similar in form and tone to what I was writing and supported me in bringing my formatting in closer communication with what we were seeing in those other works.

Meredith paid careful attention to my use of characterization. She brought to my conscious attention the ways I'd used aspects of myself and the ways I perform myself in public in order to write the various characters, and also helped me notice how (M)athematician was more distinctly characterized than the other characters. She also directly connected M's unfiltered speech to her experiences with Mathematicians and how unrestrained they often were in expressing their thoughts – as a cultural insider, this observation resonated with my own experiences as well. Building on those observations, I applied those ideas to the other characters, both giving them "more personality" with more moments of distinct characterization and also connecting their personality metaphorically with aspects of their disciplines: (T)eacher Educator was rewritten to speak more poetically more often, reflecting my views of teaching children as performance art; (C)ritical Historian was rewritten to be more visibly reflective, often looking past or beyond what is in front of her, traits originally reflective of my own neurodivergence/autism now drawing analogy with how Critical Historians are divergent from Historians writ broad; and (B)artender was redrafted to more explicitly adopt the tone and cadence of a social justice activist.

Meredith paid careful attention to my broader use of visual or auditory cues and metaphors to support the rest of the work. For example, in the first draft, Meredith noted that M's monologue was the most engaging, especially insofar as he was the only character who had visuals or activity accompanying his speech. I revised the paper to incorporate visual or performance cues to the other monologues, both to make them more engaging and to amplify their messages through visual or other performance metaphor.

Meredith also supported me in making many other small changes that improve the overall readability of the play, such as adding additional references to Bartender prior to their more active engagement with the story.

In short, Meredith provided me with perspective that this work absolutely needed given the centrality of form to its overall goal, but which the various mathematics education scholars who had previously offered feedback were not well-positioned to offer. To those interested in the intersection between education research and art (and to those who haven't yet taken time to consider this intersection), I would cite this experience as an extremely positive one, one which allowed me to produce a work both better written and denser in meaning.

Acknowledgements

This article is adapted from Bowers (2021). Copyright © 2021 D. M. Bowers.

References

- Bowers, D. M. (2021). *Anarchist mathematics education: Ethic, motivation, and praxis* (Publication # 18446) [Doctoral dissertation, Michigan State University]. Proquest.
- Corwin, R. B. (1989). Multiplication as original sin. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 8, 223–225.
- Harkness, S. S., & Thomas, J. (2008). Reflections on “multiplication as original sin”: The implications of using a case to help preservice teachers understand invented algorithms. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 27, 128-137.
- Kendi, I. X. (2016). *Stamped from the beginning: The definitive history of racist ideas in America*. Nation Books.
- Lakatos, I. (1976). *Proofs and refutations: The logic of mathematical discovery*. University of Cambridge Press.
- Sakai, J. (2014). *Settlers: The mythology of the white proletariat from Mayflower to modern*. PM Press. (Original work published 1983)